

SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article examines in detail the relevance of the work of a social teacher at school in modern conditions, as well as the content of the work of a social teacher in a secondary school.

Introduction

The field of activity of a social teacher is society as the closest environment of a person, human relations, socio-cultural conditions of development. What kind of society do we have? In the last ten years, social problems such as want and poverty, alcoholism and drug addiction, unemployment, vagrancy and social orphanhood, crime and violent behavior have flourished. I'm not even talking about national conflicts and terrorism, environmental and man-made disasters.

It must be admitted that there is a social bottom in modern Russia. Moreover, not everything is determined by material well-being. Loss of value orientations plays an important role here. The environment inclines its conformal representatives to quickly solve their problems by various asocial, sometimes simply criminal methods. Whole sections of the population fall to the social bottom: disabled people, single mothers, refugees, unemployed, large families.

The family as a whole is currently experiencing a crisis, while value norms and rules, love, care, sympathy, responsibility are nurtured in the family. Working with a problem family is a priority in the activities of a social teacher.

The modern school is in dire need of support and development of a system of social and psychological support for students. The growth of juvenile delinquency, adolescent drug addiction, computer addiction and "virtual" aggression in children, the lack of a system of universal values among the younger generation (tolerance, communication skills, culture) - all these problems are acutely faced by the school and society as a whole. Their solution is impossible without the professional work of specialized specialists - social educators and psychologists. The sphere of professional duties of social educators includes working with children, adolescents, youth and their parents, adults in a family and household environment, with adolescent and youth groups, associations.

This means that the main sphere of activity of a social teacher is society (the sphere of the immediate environment of the individual, the sphere of human relations). At the same time, the priority (especially in modern conditions) is the sphere of relations in the family and its immediate environment, at the place of residence. A social educator works with children, their families, family and neighborhood environment and the purpose of his activity is to organize preventive, socially significant activities of children and adults in society. The tasks of the practical activity of a social teacher include a very wide field of activity from direct work with a child who has problems with socialization in the surrounding society to all social organizations and social institutions involved in the social education of the younger generation.

Material and Methods

Social workers are increasingly involved in the process of socialization and personality formation. In our country, both social teachers and social workers work in the education system, who help children and adults to overcome certain life difficulties.

Social pedagogy as a practical activity is focused mainly on working with children and families. If the parents, for some reason, are not able to assist the child in solving his problems, the social educator seeks to fulfill this task. Social work at school is designed to focus mainly on those shortcomings that teachers, students and their parents point out, applying alternative concepts to eliminate them.

Depending on the profile, the place of work of a social teacher may be:

- social and pedagogical services of educational institutions (preschool educational institutions, institutions of additional education, general education

schools, special correctional educational institutions, lyceums, gymnasiums, boarding schools, orphanages, secondary specialized educational institutions, universities);

- social services of specialized institutions (rehabilitation centers, social shelters);

- services of municipal bodies (guardianship and custody bodies, centers of social psychological and pedagogical assistance, departments for social protection of the population, departments of social assistance to families and children).

Thus, the social educator:

- organizes educational work in the classroom, group, hostel, on the course, stream, in the platoon of educational institutions, aimed at the formation of a general culture of the individual, adaptation of the individual to life in society, respect for the surrounding nature;

- studies the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of the individual and its microenvironment, living conditions, identifies interests and needs, difficulties and problems, conflict situations, behavioral deviations and provides timely social assistance and support to students and pupils;

- acts as an intermediary between an individual and an educational institution, family, environment, authorities;

- promotes the realization of the rights and freedoms of students, the creation of a comfortable and safe environment, ensuring the protection of their life and health;

- creates conditions for the development of talents, mental and physical abilities of students outside the classroom;

- interacts with teachers, parents (persons replacing them), specialists of social services, family and youth employment services and other services in assisting students, children in need of custody and

guardianship, children with disabilities, as well as those in extreme situations;

- participates in the development, approval and implementation of educational programs of the institution, is responsible for the quality of their implementation within the limits of its competence.

Socio-pedagogical activity is social work, including pedagogical activity, aimed at helping a child (adolescent) in organizing himself, his psychological state, at establishing normal relations in the family, at school, in society. In the field of social protection, the main directions of social work were determined, which the social teacher is also involved in. It:

- provision of material assistance (cash, patronage, benefits and benefits, help in everyday life);

- organization of social care (working with people, recruiting employees, checking, promoting best practices);

- impact on a person.

The process of influencing a person is a process of pedagogical and psychological influence. This is done by a social worker, a social educator. The content of the work of a social teacher in accordance with the qualification characteristics is determined by its pedagogical orientation. This means that all his professional activities are essentially a set of measures for the upbringing, education, development and social protection of the individual in institutions and at the place of residence of students.

Conclusion

So, the work of a modern general education school as an open socio-pedagogical system presupposes the expansion of its upbringing and educational functions, care for the humanization of the environment surrounding the child, initiative

in socio-pedagogical activity in the microdistrict. Educational institutions are acquiring a new social role, contributing to the formation of promising cultural and educational models. It is social pedagogical work that makes it possible to make such changes in the upbringing system of children and adolescents that provide optimal conditions for their personal development, social protection, socialization in accordance with the UN Convention on Rights child.

The social educator ensures that social work is active, including the children themselves and their parents in social work.

The social educator studies the interests of children, the problems of family relations with different lifestyles, - he studies the family, helps her in crisis situations, helps in improving the environment, in improving the psychological and pedagogical culture of the environment, protects the interests of the child, and establishes contacts.

But, unfortunately, today there are schools that do not yet have social educators. But the good news is that his functions are partially performed by the deputy director for educational work or some class teachers. For example, they can visit the families of students, they can keep records of disadvantaged families for themselves, hold meetings and talks with such families, but they do not have the right to provide official social assistance to students. Social educators have such rights. Therefore, their presence at school is irreplaceable.

But since this profession is relatively young, there is hope that schools that do not yet have social teachers will not have long to wait, I want to believe that this profession will be in great demand. And future school social educators need to know that they are expected and needed.

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